

Maternal stress during pregnancy and Early childhood development

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Abstract:

We estimate the causal impact of prenatal stress on early childhood cognitive and socio-emotional development, using exogenously-induced stress caused by a strong earthquake in Chile. We find that in-utero maternal stress affects childhood skills developed by age two. Prenatal stress reduces children's cognitive skills and increases attention problems, relative to children not exposed to in-utero stress, and the effects are heterogeneous. The negative impacts on cognition occur during the first trimester of pregnancy, are concentrated on lower-income children, and among girls, meanwhile, the harmful effects on socio-emotional problems are found among high-income children and boys.

Keywords: In-utero stress; early childhood; child development; maternal stress; maternal mental health; earthquake; Chile.

JEL Classification: J13; I10; I19

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1. Introduction

There is now ample consensus that cognitive and socio-emotional skills developed in early childhood have a significant impact on future outcomes such as educational attainment, academic outcomes, wages, and overall health (see Almond et al., 2017 for a recent survey). The extensive work of Heckman and co-authors has provided a theoretical framework to understand skill formation and its dynamics,¹ with two main conclusions: first, skills developed in early childhood affect the productivity of all future investments in human capital (dynamic complementarity), and second, different types of skills affect the accumulation of other, distinct skills, i.e. cognitive abilities may promote health and vice versa (self-productivity). Since early childhood is a critical period in the formation of cognitive and socio-emotional skills, and since future human capital outcomes are impacted by this period, parents, educators and policy makers should be attentive to negative shocks during early stages of life, including the *in utero* period.²

Identification of the causal impact of in utero conditions on future outcomes is challenging because children's family background may be correlated with in utero conditions, as well as with investments in children's human capital and later outcomes. Economists have complemented the traditional epidemiological literature by improving the

¹ See Heckman, 2006; Cunha and Heckman, 2007; Heckman, 2007; Heckman and Masterov, 2007; and Heckman et al., 2006, among others.

² These conclusions are in line with what the "fetal origin hypothesis" suggests. It was developed by Barker (1992) and suggests that the in-utero period of development is critical in shaping future cognitive and socio-emotional skills, health trajectories and economic outcomes.

causal identification strategies, often appealing to different types of exogenous shocks during pregnancy to identify causal effects of in-utero conditions on child's physical health at birth, and on later human capital outcomes. In general, these studies find that in-utero exposure to events that directly affect the mother's physical health—such as infections, disease, malnutrition, and negative income shocks—leads to lower birthweight, worse future health of the child, lower educational attainment, worse educational achievement (test scores and grades), and worse labor market outcomes in adulthood.³ Research has also found that exogenous variations in the mother's level of stress during pregnancy, brought about by events such as exposure to terrorism and military conflicts, or to natural phenomena such as hurricanes or earthquakes, have negative consequences for child's birthweight, cognition, physical health and schooling outcomes.⁴ Stress can affect fetal development by exposing the fetus to stress hormones that are transported through the placenta, which are related to premature delivery and which can compromise fetal development and function; for example, stress hormones can suppress the developing immune system. These physiological impacts on the child can later result in worse health and education outcomes, which can in turn affect labor market performance.

³ Almond et al., 2015; Hoynes et al., 2016; Lavy et al., 2016; Banerjee et al., 2010; Currie and Rossin-Slater, 2013; Torche, 2011; Field et al., 2009.

⁴ Lipkind et al. (2010), Eccleston (2011), Eskenazy et al. (2007), Camacho (2008), Mansour and Rees (2011), Currie and Rossin-Slater (2013), Torche (2011), Aizer et al. (2016), and Persson and Rossin-Slater (2016).

Partly due to data limitations, this large and growing literature has focused on the effect of pre-natal shocks on children’s outcomes at birth, and then at ages seven or later.⁵ Much less is known about the impact on early childhood development outcomes between birth and age 6, known as the “middle years” or intermediate outcomes in the literature (Almond and Currie, 2017). In utero shocks may affect early development of cognitive and socio-emotional skills during the first two years of life, which will likely have a direct effect on future wages—a channel that is different than affecting early health, which in turn affects wages. Understanding the effects on intermediate outcomes could help identify individuals in need of assistance more quickly and to target interventions more effectively.

In this paper, we contribute to this gap in the literature and analyze whether in-utero stress affects a child’s early development. Our setting is exposure to stress brought about by a strong earthquake in Chile, and we study whether it affected children’s early cognitive and socio-emotional skills by about age 2. Our data contains results from several child development tests (Battelle Developmental Inventory, Child Behavior Checklist, and TADI)⁶ applied to children that were aged between 8 and 36 months two years after the earthquake; our data also includes a rich set of family background variables, including mother’s health, behaviors, and socioeconomic conditions before, during and after pregnancy.

⁵ See, among many others, Breining et al. (2015), Akee et al. (2015), Bharadwaj et al. (2017), and Baker and Milligan (2016).

⁶ TADI is the Spanish acronym for Childhood Learning and Development Test, a childhood development test designed in Chile.

Because it is impossible to predict the timing and location of earthquakes, and because all of Chile is subject to seismic movements, Chileans can't select into areas that will not be subject to earthquakes. Therefore, our identification strategy relies on the proximity of mothers' residence to the earthquake's epicenter and the random timing of pregnancy at the time of the stressful event. Our sample includes children who were in utero when the 27-F earthquake occurred, and children who were conceived afterwards.

A unique feature of our data is that it allows us to discriminate between the effects of stress and alternative mechanisms, such as changes in mothers' behaviors or income effects as a result of the earthquake. We find that stress, and not changes in wealth or behavior, is the main channel causing harm to cognitive and socio-emotional skills.

This paper has several contributions to the existing literature on in-utero transmissions of health shocks. First, it is among the first to provide evidence of whether early cognitive and socio-emotional skills are sensitive to episodes of in-utero stress, with measures of specific early childhood developmental tests. Second, we are able to discern whether the impact of earthquake-induced stress is due to the in-utero stress resulting from the event, and not to mothers' behavioral responses or other indirect effects of the event. Third, our results suggest that birthweight—commonly used as a proxy for a child's health—has limitations, since in our study, in-utero shocks that affect maternal stress do not affect birthweight, but they do affect child development at age 2.⁷ Finally, since we find negative effects of stress suffered during the first trimester, our findings suggest that policy interventions focalized on pregnant women should pay special attention to early stages of pregnancy.

⁷ This finding is consistent with the medical study in Palmeiro-Silva et al. (2018).

This paper is organized as follows: section 2 discusses in-utero health shocks and early child development; section 3 describes our data, including a description of the 27-F earthquake. In Section 4 we present our empirical methodology, followed by a section describing our results. In Section 6 we include concluding comments, implications for policy and suggestions for future research.

2. In-utero Health and Childhood Development

Physical health shocks

The epidemiological literature has extensive findings that document the effects of in utero health shocks on children's development; but in general, these studies report correlations that are estimated from small samples with few control variables (see for example Cosmi et al., 1990; Barker, 1995; Wadhwa, 1996; O'Connor et al., 2005; Abel et al., 2014).

Relatively recent studies in economics contribute to the causal identification of effects of in utero conditions on later life outcomes by exploiting exogenous and random shocks affecting pregnant mothers. There is a strand of the literature that focuses on the effect of infections; for example, studies find that prenatal exposure to an influenza pandemic led to lower high school graduation and wages later in life in the U.S., while exposure to the Asian flu in Great Britain led to lower academic achievement measured by test scores (Almond, 2006; Kelly, 2009). Interestingly, while birth weight was reduced by prenatal flu exposure, the effect appears to be independent of later test score effects. Maternal malnutrition due to the 1959-1961 Chinese famine was associated with higher illiteracy, as well as worse labor market and marriage outcomes Almond et al. (2010), whilst a cohort of Swedish children who were exposed in-utero to the 1986 Chernobyl accident radiation

performed substantially worse in school, though there was no future health damage Almond et al. (2009).

Others have focused on the effects of nutritional changes during pregnancy and later outcomes; for example, Field et al. (2009) found that prenatal iodine supplementation raised educational attainment in Tanzania by half a year of schooling, with larger impacts for girls. Almond et al. (2015) use the month-long Ramadan fast as a natural experiment to examine whether Ramadan's overlap with pregnancy affects subsequent academic outcomes at age 7; they found that test scores are 0.05-0.08 standard deviations lower for students exposed to Ramadan in early pregnancy. Hoynes et al. (2016) innovate and examine the impact of the introduction of the Food Stamp Program in the U.S., which increased economic resources available in-utero and during childhood, finding that the Food Stamp program has beneficial effects on children decades after initial exposure through the reduction in the incidence of "metabolic syndrome" (obesity, high blood pressure, and diabetes), and higher economic self-sufficiency among women. In a related line of research, Lavy et al. (2016) use quasi-experimental variation created by the immigration of Ethiopian Jews to Israel in May 1991, exploiting the fact that children in-utero faced dramatic differences in medical care technologies, prenatal conditions, and prenatal care prior to immigration from Ethiopia to Israel. One of the major differences was adequacy of micronutrient supplements, particularly iodine, iron and folic acid. They found that children exposed to better environmental conditions in utero at earlier stages of pregnancy have higher educational attainment (lower repetition and dropout rates and higher Baccalaureate rate) and higher education quality (achieve a higher proficiency level in their Baccalaureate diploma) two decades later.

A third strand of the literature has focused on the effect of income shocks during pregnancy, for example, Banerjee et al. (2010) study the XIX century blight to French vineyards from the phylloxera insect, which decreased wine production and income, and found a negative effect on affected children's height (0.5-0.9 centimetres shorter in adulthood).

Common to these studies is the use of exogenous environmental or policy driven shocks that occur during the prenatal period, to study short-term health outcomes on the offspring (such as birthweight, mortality, and gestational length) or long run outcomes such as educational attainment, graduation rates, wages, marriage outcomes, and height, among others.

Maternal mental health and stress and future outcomes

A large medical literature has studied the inter-generational effect of pregnant mothers' stress on fetal health. Maternal stress can affect fetal development through various channels: first, through the exposure of the fetus to stress hormones that are transported through the placenta, which are in turn related to premature delivery and which can also compromise fetal development and function (Stott, 1973; Myers, 1975). Additionally, stress may suppress the developing immune system, which could account for the higher incidence of respiratory and other infections in the infants. And finally, mothers' behavior may change in response to stressful events, specifically, stress may induce high-risk behaviors such as drinking alcohol, smoking, poor diet, etc., and these behaviors may affect fetal development and health (Dunkel-Schetter, 2009).

The economics literature has analyzed the impact of exogenous shocks to mother's in-utero mental health on children's future outcomes by focusing on in-utero stress episodes.

Different methodologies have been applied to establish a causal effect of stress on future child's outcomes. A widely used identification strategy is to infer causality by exploiting geographic exposure to stressful episodes. Examples include the September 11 terrorist attacks (Lipkind et al., 2010; Eccleston, 2011; Eskenazy et al., 2007), landmine explosions in Colombia (Camacho, 2008), political conflict in the West Bank and Gaza (Mansour and Reeds, 2011) and Korea (Lee, 2014); terrorist attacks in Spain (Quintana-Domeneque and Rodenas-Serrano, 2017); and an earthquake in Northern Chile (Torche, 2011; 2018). These studies identify effects by exploiting geographic proximity to stress—i.e., they compare women living or working in the area affected by a stressful event under the assumption that women further away experienced less stress, or none at all.

Other methodologies include sibling or mother-fixed effects to identify impacts of in-utero stress exposure. For example, Aizer et al. (2016) finds that in-utero stress exposure has little effect on birth weight but has a significant, negative impact on school attainment and verbal IQ scores, and exposed children are more likely to have a chronic health condition at age 7. Currie and Rossin-Slater (2013) finds that exposure to hurricanes during pregnancy increases the probability of abnormal conditions of the newborn, with no effects on the incidence of low birth weight or gestation length.

A final approach uses random dates of conception and pregnancy at the moment a stressful event occurs to identify effects. Recently, Persson and Rossin-Slater (2016) studies the effect of in-utero exposure to maternal stress from family ruptures (deaths) on children's birth weight and future outcomes, finding that pre-natal exposure to the death of a maternal relative increases take-up of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) medications during childhood and anti-anxiety and depression medications in adulthood;

lowers birth weight; and raises the risk of perinatal complications that require hospitalization.

To the best of our knowledge, none of the studies discussed above has analyzed the impact of in-utero maternal mental health on early childhood development between ages 0-5 years. Our study contributes to fill this gap in what we currently know about maternal stress effects on early childhood.

3. Data

Our main source of data is the Early Childhood Longitudinal Survey (ELPI, for its Spanish acronym) carried out in Chile in 2010 and 2012.⁸ ELPI is a longitudinal survey designed to be representative of the population of children from 6 months to 7 years at the national level, which collects information on several socio-economic dimensions of the child, her parents, and the household. The main purpose of ELPI is to apply and collect information from several developmental tests that are applied to the child, as well as test results that measure cognitive and socio-emotional skills of the main caretaker (overwhelmingly mothers; henceforth we refer to them interchangeably).

The ELPI 2012 wave included data on children born between September 1st 2009 and December 31st 2011. The data includes weeks of gestation, and since we were granted access to child's date of birth, we calculated the approximate date of conception so that our final sample includes children who were in-utero on 27-F and children who were conceived after the earthquake. The test instruments were applied the children in our sample in 2012, and they were aged between 7 to 36 months.

⁸ The Spanish name of the survey is *Encuesta Longitudinal de Primera Infancia* (ELPI).

3.1. Children's cognitive and socio-emotional outcomes

The tests that were applied to measure child development were age-specific, and given the ages of the children in our sample, we include results from the Battelle Developmental Inventory (BDI), Childhood Learning and Development Test (TADI for its Spanish acronym),⁹ and the Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL). The BDI screens and evaluates early childhood developmental milestones.¹⁰ It assessed 100 items grouped in five areas: personal-social, adaptive, motor, communication, and cognitive; only the average score for the BDI is reported in the data. TADI is an instrument designed to measure learning in four dimensions: cognition, motor, language, and socioemotional skills (similar to the BDI). Each of these dimensions generates a separate measurement, along with an aggregate measure that includes the average of all four. Its administration combines observation by the test taker, the application of the test, and self-reporting from the main caretaker.

The CBCL assesses behavior and socio-emotional competencies of the child as reported by the parents, and can be used to identify problematic areas in child development (Achenbach and Rescorla, 2000). The CBCL asked the main caretaker to respond to 99 behaviors of the child, and then grouped them into seven clinical syndromes included in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of the American Psychiatric Association, DSM V (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). The ELPI data reports aggregate CBCL results for all behaviors, as well as three categories: internalization, externalization, and sleep problems. The *internalization* category includes syndromes that involve only the child: emotional reactivity, anxiety/depression, somatic complaints, and autism. The

⁹ *Test de Aprendizaje de Desarrollo Infantil.*

¹⁰ Screening Test, 2nd ed. (BDI-ST2) (Newborg, Stock and Wnek, 1996).

externalization category includes problems that involve conflicts with other people and the expectations about the child (such as attention problems and aggressive behavior), and the *sleep problems* syndrome stands alone.

The ELPI data reports age-adjusted, standardized test scores, distributed with mean equal to 50 and standard deviation equal to 10 (denominated T-scores in the educational assessment literature); to facilitate interpretation, we standardized the T-scores to have a mean of zero and standard deviation equal to 1. The data did not report T-scores for each of the CBCL syndromes; however, it reported the percentile of each child in the distribution. In the case of the CBCL, a larger value indicates greater behavior problems or socio-emotional difficulties. The BDI and TADI tests were applied to children aged 7 to 36 months old, and the CBCL was applied to children aged between 18 and 36 months.

Table 1 reports descriptive statistics of the test results for our final sample of children; an asterisk indicates whether variables are statistically different across regions. We can observe that in general, children in areas that were affected by the 27-F earthquake had similar performance on the tests, relative to children in areas that were not (see discussion below regarding the definition of earthquake and non-earthquake regions)

3.2. Earthquakes and Maternal Stress

The earthquake in our setting occurred on February 27th, 2010. With a magnitude of 8.8 on the Richter scale, it shocked the valleys and coastal regions of central Chile (where about 80 percent of the country's population live) for more than three minutes, and it was the fifth largest earthquake ever recorded by a seismograph. Appendix 1 reports information regarding observed intensities by Astroza et al. (2010) and also reports estimated average intensities at the municipal level for the six regions most affected by the

earthquake; we classify the 2012 municipality of residence of each child as an earthquake-affected area based on this information.¹¹

Aftershocks continued for several weeks after the main event; during the 27th and 28th of February there were 214 aftershocks of magnitude 5.0 or more on the Richter scale (including one aftershock of 7.4 magnitude); during the month of March, 187 aftershocks above 5.0 were registered, including a 7.0 earthquake. By April and May, the number of strong aftershocks had significantly decreased to 25 and 15, respectively. The earthquake and its immediate aftershocks, therefore, had the potential of generating high levels of stress, anxiety, panic or other mental health problems of varying degrees among a large fraction of the population, even in parts of the country that were not directly affected by it.

An important body of research has studied the consequences of natural disasters (including earthquakes) on individuals' health, including mental health (Carr et al., 1997; Galea et al., 2005; Najarian et al., 2001, among others). The evidence concludes that the main effects of large earthquakes on mental health are related to post traumatic stress disorders (PTSD). Typically, individuals with PTSD may re-experience the event via intrusive memories, flashbacks and nightmares, avoid anything that reminds them of the trauma, and have anxious feelings they did not have before that are so intense their lives are disrupted. The symptoms can last more than six months and cause significant impairment in social, occupational, or other important areas of functioning (Bhalotra et al., 2012). Regarding the persistence of the effects, previous psychological and psychiatric evidence finds that general distress levels following an earthquake return to normal after about 12

¹¹ We follow Astroza et al. (2010) and classified as earthquake regions those reported in Figure A1.1. See the details of the Mercalli scale in Table A1.1 in the appendix.

months, but post-traumatic stress reactions do not fade until 18 months after the earthquake (Karanci and Rustemli, 1995; Shinfuku, 1999). The prevalence of PTSD varies widely in earthquake survivors due to different exposures and proximity to the epicenter of the earthquake (Luo et al., 2012; Fukuda et al., 2000; Glynn et al., 2001).

Due to its magnitude, several surveys in Chile—including ELPI’s second wave— included questions related to the earthquake and its effects. The question most relevant to this study asked mothers to recall whether they suffered a series of stress-related symptoms that she could attribute directly to the 27-F earthquake. The symptoms were: insomnia (difficulty in falling sleep or early waking up); stress, anguish or anxiety; crying or emotional instability; fear or panic; traumatic memories of the earthquake; and other effects. Although it was not a screen for PTSD, this ELPI question contains many of the symptoms that characterize post-traumatic stress disorder as defined by the American Psychiatric Association’s Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-V). With this information, we created a binary variable indicating maternal stress if a mother reported any of the five symptoms described above.¹²

Across the country, an average of 36 percent of mothers experienced at least one of the symptoms of stress as a result of 27-F (Table 1), with significant differences across earthquake regions: 42 percent of mothers in earthquake-affected regions experienced stress as a direct consequence of the 27-F earthquake, compared to 16 percent in non-earthquake regions. In Table 2 we report the incidence of the specific stress-related symptoms across regions. Interestingly, a significant fraction of women report suffering symptoms in

¹² We did not consider the response “Other symptoms” because it did not allow us to identify whether the symptom was related to stress in a precise way.

regions that were not directly affected by the 27-F earthquake; as expected, however, stress symptoms are more than 4 times more likely in earthquake regions, and traumatic memories are at least 12 times more likely.

4. Methodology

Our aim is to estimate the effect of maternal stress during pregnancy on children's early cognitive and socio-emotional outcomes. Previous studies approximate maternal stress with geographic exposure shocks and estimate relationships such as the following:

$$y_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 IU_i + \alpha_2 T_i + \alpha_3 (T_i \times IU_i) + X_i \delta + u_i \quad (1)$$

where y_i is the outcome of child i ; IU_i is a binary variable that is equal to 1 if the child was in-utero at the time of the shock;¹³ T_i is a binary variable indicating whether the mother lived in or near the area exposed to a traumatic or stress-inducing event; X_i is a vector of controls and u_i is an idiosyncratic error term.

Identification of the effect of in-utero stress comes from the interaction term, and α_3 is the difference-in-difference estimator. The identifying assumptions of our reduced-form model are that the date and location of the earthquake and the timing of pregnancies are uncorrelated with observed and unobserved characteristics of the child or her family.

¹³ As was previously discussed, the earthquake was followed by a period of frequent and strong aftershocks, so instead of a single date, we define an earthquake episode beginning on the 27th of February and ending the last week of March, which is the period with the greatest concentration of high-intensity earthquakes. We consider children to be in-utero if their mothers were pregnant during the weeks between February 27 and March 31, 2010. We estimate the date of conception from the date of birth and weeks of gestation at birth.

Although we cannot test our assumption directly, Table 1 (columns 4 through 9) reveals that maternal, child and household characteristics are not significantly different between earthquake and non-earthquake regions, nor between children who were in-utero on 27-F or conceived afterwards. Furthermore, the fact that the fraction of in-utero children it is the same across earthquake and non-earthquake regions supports the idea that pregnancy decisions were orthogonal to the earthquake occurrence.

We believe our assumption of orthogonality to unobservables is reasonable because first, earthquakes are not predictable events, thus it is unlikely that pregnancy timings would have been affected by the likelihood of the earthquake. Second, Chile is among the countries with greatest seismic activity in the world, and the whole country is located on an active fault off the coast and potentially subject to large earthquakes. Therefore, it is not possible for people to self-select into non-earthquake areas. Thus, the timing and location of the earthquake can be reasonably considered as an exogenous shock.

The vector of control variables, X_i , includes mothers' age, age squared, years of schooling, and cognitive and socio-emotional development measured her test results on the Wechsler Adults Intelligence Scale (WAIS) test and the Big Five Inventory (BFI) test in its five categories: extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism, and openness to experiences. We also control for child's sex, birth order, age (in months), and number of siblings; and for household income per capita, whether the father lives in household, and binary variables indicating prior mental health issues of the mother, father, or other relatives. Finally, we also incorporate a series of regional dummy variables to control for systematic differences across the fifteen administrative regions of the country.

Is it stress?

Measuring stress with geographic exposure to an event, as in equation (1), assumes that mother's stress (which we denote by s_i) is a reaction to the earthquake (T_i), and that this reaction is the same for all individuals exposed to the shock. This can be expressed as

$$s_i = f(T_i) \quad (2)$$

In most of the literature, this relationship is binary and defined based on geographic proximity or residence in an affected area. This specification has several assumptions. First, it assumes that all women within proximity of the shock are affected; second, it assumes that the shock has the same intensity for all women in the affected area, and third, that women in areas not affected by the shock did not suffer stress. These three assumptions can be easily violated, as it is possible that women in the affected area do get not stressed; that some shocks vary in their intensity—such as earthquakes—and women exposed to higher magnitudes are more likely to suffer stress; and finally, women living in non-affected regions may also suffer from stress induced by the shock.¹⁴

A more flexible specification that allows for heterogeneous individual responses to the same event, including being stressed in areas not affected by the shock, could take the following form:

$$S_i = f_i(T_i) \quad (3)$$

In our setting, stress was exogenously induced by the 27-F earthquake, and each woman responded differently to the same event. Since our data contains a self-reported measure of stress *induced by 27-F*, we also estimate a model in which we include a direct,

¹⁴ For instance, from worrying about family members or friends that live in affected areas.

individual-level measure of maternal stress. The reduced form model that we estimate is the following:

$$y_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 IU_i + \alpha_2 S_i(T_i) + \alpha_3 (S_i(T_i) \times IU_i) + X_i \delta + u_i \quad (4)$$

The interaction between self-reported maternal stress and being in-utero on 27-F allows us to estimate the differential effect of pre-natal maternal stress on child development. Our parameter of interest is α_3 which is interpreted as the in-utero effect on child development due to the maternal stress actually induced by the earthquake episode. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to measure shock-induced stress directly, and to thereby account for individual heterogeneity in mothers' susceptibility to stress.

5. Results

We present results of the effect of geographic exposure to the earthquake (equation 1, above) on early childhood development outcomes in Table 3. We include two measures of exposure: a binary variable that equals one if in 2012 mothers were living in the municipalities that were affected by the 27-F earthquake, and a (continuous) measure of the intensity of the earthquake measured on the Mercalli scale.¹⁵ The first row contains the difference-in-difference estimates; as Table 3 reveals, exposure to the earthquake did not have an effect on early childhood development as measured by test results on the Batelle Development Inventory, average TADI, and the Child Behavior Checklist. The control variables have the expected signs; notably, we find that mothers' prior mental health issues and problematic personality traits (low extraversion, low agreeableness, high neuroticism)

¹⁵ See the details of the Mercalli scale in Table A1.1 in the appendix.

are correlated with greater child behavioral problems, while girls and children with more educated mothers have better performance on the BDI and TADI tests.

The coefficients for the impact of earthquake exposure have the expected signs in most specifications, i.e., the reduce BDI and TADI results and increase behavior problems as proxied by the CBCL; however, they are not statistically significant at standard levels. It is possible that this result is due to (i) heterogeneous effects of the shock on individual women; or (ii) misrepresentation of mothers' region of residence due to migration to or from earthquake regions between 2010 and 2012. Secondary data from a nationally representative post-earthquake household survey, CASEN-EPT,¹⁶ reveals that migration as a result of the earthquake occurred in less than 2% of the population, so that possibility (ii) is unlikely.

Our data allows us to control for heterogeneous effects of the earthquake through the individual question to mothers that asks whether, as a result of the 27-F earthquake, they suffered symptoms of PTSD. As discussed in Section 4, an event such as the 27-F earthquake is likely to cause different reactions among the population living in proximity to the affected areas, and also on individuals who did not live in the region.

¹⁶ The CASEN-EPT (Post Earthquake Survey for its Spanish acronym) is a household survey that was a follow up to the 2009 national CASEN household survey. The EPT was implemented in April 2010 (about one month after the earthquake) on a sub-sample of the CASEN households surveyed in 2009. The EPT included questions regarding the frequency and intensity of 17 stress symptoms as a direct consequence of the 27-F earthquake.

We present our estimates of the impact of (self-reported) in-utero stress on childhood development outcomes in Table 4. In columns (1) through (3), we include the estimated effects for children living throughout the country and in columns (4) through (6) we present results for a sub-group of children whose mothers reside in municipalities that were affected by the 27-F earthquake. It is plausible that mothers living in the most affected regions suffered higher stress so that point estimates are of a larger magnitude; however, there is a trade off because the smaller sample size may affect statistical significance. We omit other control variables henceforth.¹⁷

Our results reveal that suffering earthquake-induced stress during pregnancy harms early childhood development as measured by the BDI test score, with a reduction of 0.17 standard deviations (column 1 of Table 4). The point estimate for the TADI test indicates a negative effect (column 2), whilst the effect on the CBCL test is positive (column 3), which means that in-utero stress caused more behavior problems. Neither of these results are statistically significant. Results for children in earthquake-affected areas in columns (4) through (6) are similar to the general results; henceforth, we will present and discuss results for all children only.¹⁸

Is mothers' stress exogenous?

¹⁷ Other characteristics have the expected signs; full results available upon request from the authors.

¹⁸ All tables include all children; results for earthquake areas are similar, available upon request.

A threat to identification would occur if reported earthquake-induced stress is correlated to mothers' unobserved characteristics. We cannot examine this directly with our data, but we can assess whether the self-reported measure of stress was induced by the earthquake and whether it is sensitive to the inclusion of mothers' characteristics. In Table 5 (column 1) we report the estimated effect of the intensity of the 27-F earthquake on the probability that a mother suffers from earthquake-induced stress. We find that a larger earthquake magnitude had a positive and highly significant effect on reported maternal stress (column 1 of Table 5).¹⁹

Another potential threat to identification would be if the earthquake occurred in areas where women were more likely to experience stress, or areas with higher (lower) socio-economic conditions that can affect stress. If earthquake intensity is unrelated to these variables, the magnitude of its measured effect will be robust to the inclusion of such variables in the regression. In Columns 2 and 3 of Table 5, we incorporate antecedents of family members' mental health (as a proxy for stress susceptibility) and socio-demographic conditions, respectively; we find that the impact of the earthquake on self-reported stress is robust to inclusion of these variables, so it is unlikely that they are correlated. From these results, we conclude that the self-reported measure of stress is driven by the earthquake, consistent with the survey question's intent.

Other mechanisms: Wealth and income effects?

¹⁹ We estimated these effects with a binary measure of earthquake exposure and found similar results; available from the authors upon request.

As with every natural disaster, there may be several mechanisms through which the disaster causes stress or mental health problems, such as decline in income, loss of employment, physical health problems, death of a relative, house damage or loss, among others. We use the CASEN-EPT—which contains household’s socio-economic information before and after the earthquake in the areas affected by the earthquake—to explore whether the 27-F earthquake might have operated through some of these alternative mechanisms.

Table 6 reports statistics on key variables before and after the earthquake, in affected and non-affected regions. Although no mental health questions were included in the pre-earthquake 2009 CASEN, we find that post-earthquake, mental health was worse in regions that were directly affected by the earthquake relative to non-affected areas in the rest of the country (which is similar to our findings with ELPI data). The variables that capture mental health disorders (frequency and intensity) are almost three times higher in regions affected by 27-F relative to the rest of the country.

Other health and socio-economic variables did not experience relevant changes that could explain such large differences in mental health. For example, fetal mortality rates present similar trends in affected and not affected regions, as well as the percentage of people living in rural areas, married, or average years of education. In terms of employment, the fraction of adults working was two percentage point lower in earthquake regions (compared to no change in unaffected regions); the magnitude of the change is relatively small.²⁰ In terms of health, a self-reported index of general health shows no major

²⁰ Given the relevance of the labor market for mental health (Powdthavee and Vernoit, 2013; Layard, 2013; Kronenberg et al., 2015) we analyzed the impact of the earthquake on labor market outcomes in the CASEN-EPT dataset, and found no significant changes in

changes after the earthquake, and only 2.7% of the individuals reported health problems due to the earthquake.

Another, source of stress, housing quality, shows a minor deterioration in regions not affected by the earthquake, and no changes in earthquake regions.²¹ Finally, income is higher in non-affected regions, although both regions experienced similar decreases in income (with a smaller decline in earthquake regions).²² These relatively minor changes in socio-economic, health, and infrastructure variables cannot explain the large differences in mental health indicators observed, suggesting that the differences in stress were most likely due to the direct exposure to a forceful, stress-inducing shock, and not to indirect effects of the earthquakes that may also cause stress.

Other mechanisms: Mothers' behaviors and decisions?

occupations by region; 1.8% of the individuals lost their job and 1.3% of the individuals did not search for a job because of the earthquake; 88% of individuals reported working in the same job, 11% changed job for other reasons, and 0.9% changed jobs because of the earthquake. Although 17% of workplaces were affected by the earthquake, two thirds report minor damages.

²¹ Regarding housing, a 98% of the people live in the same place than in 2009 and among the 2% who change residence, 1.3% was due to the earthquake. Approximately 71% of houses did not suffer any damage, 21% suffered minor damages, 5.7% suffered major damages and only 1.4% were destroyed by the earthquake

²² Wages are higher in regions not affected by the earthquake due to concentration of mining activity in these areas.

The earthquake likely affected mothers in many ways, so that our measure of maternal stress may capture other effects of the earthquake that impact early childhood development. We explore whether alternative indirect channels might explain our results; the channels include: health effects during the pregnancy (which have been widely studied in the literature), changes in mothers' behavior as a response to stress, and decisions regarding child care and employment after the child was born. For example, if the earthquake induced premature births—which then affect children's outcomes—then our identification strategy would be challenged.

To assess this possibility, we followed two approaches. First, we re-estimated regressions in Table 4 and incorporated variables that measure several alternative channels as control variables. If these are correlated with the effect of in-utero stress, then the coefficient of stress will change once these channels are included. As a second approach, we estimated whether the alternative channels were directly affected by in-utero stress from 27-F.

The results of the first approach are summarized in Table 7. As a baseline, in Column 1 we present the estimated effect of in-utero stress without including any of the alternative channels (i.e., the same coefficient as column 1 of Table 4); we omit the coefficients of all the other control variables for ease of exposition. Next, in each column we display the coefficients of the effects of in-utero stress and each alternative channel we analyze (columns 2 through 9), which is described in each column title. The alternative channels we explored (due to data availability) are: number of complications during labor; whether the birth was premature (<37 weeks gestation); child's weight-for-height at birth (z-score); whether the mother smoked, drank alcohol, or consumed recreational drugs during the

pregnancy; childcare take-up after birth; and mothers' months of employment during the 6 months after the earthquake. The dependent variables in Table 6 are: the BDI test (Panel A), the TADI test (Panel B), and the average CBCL (Panel C).

If the estimated effect of stress is due to the alternative channels, we should observe changes in the estimated coefficient of maternal stress when we include these channels in the regressions. We find that this is not the case: in all Panels of Table 7, we find that the estimated effects of in-utero stress are robust to the inclusion of these measures, suggesting that the estimated effect of stress in utero is not correlated to other explanations. Additionally, we find that complications during labor and premature births are correlated with lower childhood development measured by the BDI and TADI test (columns 2, 3 of Panels A and B). Also, we find that lower birth weight and alcohol consumption during pregnancy reduce scores on the TADI test (columns 4 and 6 of Panel B), and formal child care is correlated with improved early childhood development (column 8 of Panel B). Childhood behaviors as measured by the CBCL are not affected by the alternative channels.

The second approach to analyze the role of alternative explanations is summarized in Table 8. The dependent variable in each column is each alternative channel discussed above, and columns report the effect of in-utero stress on each of the eight alternative channels (other control variables are not shown). We can observe that the stress experienced by mothers from 27-F did not significantly affect most of the channels (the exception is use of child care after the child was born, which is lower for mothers who experienced stress). Results in Tables 7 and 8 suggest that alternative channels are not systematically correlated to the negative effects that in-utero stress has on early childhood development.

Dimensions of Child Development

Some of the tests that were applied to children in the ELPI survey are designed to measure different dimensions of their development. We analyze whether in-utero stress had an impact on specific areas of development for the two tests for which such data is available: TADI and CBCL. TADI studies four dimension of learning: cognition, motor skills, language and socio-emotional competencies. The CBCL test has three aggregate categories: internalization, externalization and sleep problems, with internalization including problems of emotional reactivity, anxiety/depression, somatic complaints, and autism. Externalization includes attention problems and aggressive behavior. Sleep problems are a stand-alone category. Table 9 reports results of the dimensions evaluated with TADI and Table 10 the different problems measured in the CBCL.

Interestingly, although in-utero stress exposure did not affect the average TADI test performance, we find that it does have a deleterious effect in some specific areas of child development. As Table 9 shows it reduces cognitive skills by 0.17 standard deviations (column 2 of Table 9). At the same time, in-utero stress exposure increases attention problems (column 8 of Table 10).

Heterogeneous effects by Trimester

Although biological evidence of the link between stress and cortisol-producing hormones is conclusive, the question about which period of pregnancy is more susceptible to shocks is still unresolved (Torche, 2011). One approach indicates that maternal stress later in the pregnancy—particularly in the third trimester—is more influential because stress-induced CRH alters the physiology of parturition, producing uterine contractions that result in early delivery (Wadhwa et al., 2004). On the other hand, De Weerth and Buitelaar

(2005) suggest that stress early in the pregnancy has greater consequences and as pregnancy advances, physiological changes lead to dampened maternal responses to stress. These changes protect women from the consequences of stress later in the pregnancy but leave them vulnerable early on. Furthermore, early maternal stress initiates a chain of events leading to preterm labor by triggering CRH gene expression in the placenta, which sets a biological clock for early delivery months later (Sandman et al., 2006).

Among women who were pregnant on 27-F, we explored whether experiencing stress as a result of the earthquake had different impacts on their child's development outcomes depending on the trimester of pregnancy at the time of the earthquake episode, relative to mothers that did not suffer stress. We present our results in Table 11, including estimates for the test averages as well as each of their dimensions (when available). Our findings suggest that suffering in-utero stress during the first trimester of pregnancy negatively affects socio-emotional development as measured by the BDI and the socio-emotional dimension of the TADI test (columns 1 and 6 of Table 11, respectively); both outcomes are reduced by approximately 0.2 standard deviations as a result of pre-natal stress.

The results are less clear regarding children's behavioral problems, however, they suggest that the exposure to stress during the third trimester increases behaviors associated to anxiety and depression (column 9), and attention (column 12). Attention problems are also worse if the child's mother suffered stress in the first trimester, and in-utero stress in the second trimester leads to children's sleep problems (column 14). Although our results cannot be considered conclusive with regards to the timing of stress exposure, they suggest that timing of exposure during pregnancy may affect dimensions of childhood development

differently, which could reconcile the apparent disagreement in the medical field. To draw more definite conclusions more research is needed.

Heterogeneous effects by household income

We also analyzed whether the effect of in-utero stress is different across socioeconomic levels. We defined households as either high- or low-income according to whether they were above or below the median of total family income per capita, respectively. Then we interacted our variable of interest—maternal stress in-utero—with the income level of the family. We present results in Table 12.

We find that in-utero stress harms childhood development of children from low-income families: suffering stress while in-utero reduces their BDI and total TADI test scores by approximately 0.2 standard deviations (columns 1 and 2, respectively). When separating TADI estimations by dimension we find that is results are driven by the negative effect on cognition, as it is reduced by 0.3 standard deviations due to in-utero stress (column 3).

In terms of behavioral problems, we find that attention problems are worsened by in-utero stress among children of high-income households (column 12 of Table 12).

Heterogeneous effects by child's sex

As a final exercise, we explored whether in-utero stress affects boys and girls differently, and report those results in Table 13. We find that pre-natal stress decreases girls' development on the cognition dimension of the TADI test by 0.2 standard deviation (column 3). For boys, we find a reduction of 0.24 standard deviations as a result of in-utero

stress in their development outcomes as measured by the BDI test (column 1). The harmful effect of stress on attention problems occurred among boys only (column 12).

6. Conclusions

The transmission of in-utero health shocks from mothers to children has been widely studied in several disciplines. In the early 1990s, epidemiologist Robert Barker was an early proponent of the “fetal origins” hypothesis, which posited that physical health conditions a fetus is exposed to will condition his future health trajectories; many have tested this hypothesis since.²³ The contribution by the field of economics has been to assess the impact of in-utero conditions with several methodologies that aim to establish a causal relation.

As early as the mid-2000s, economists began to test whether pre-natal health conditions had short and long-run impacts on a child’s birth-weight and future adult health and education outcomes. A more recent line of research has included analyses of the effects of mental health shocks during pregnancy—specifically, high levels of in-utero stress—on immediate health (birth-weight) and later outcomes (education, employment, morbidity, among others).

Less is known about the short-term effects of in-utero stress on early childhood outcomes. In this paper, we contribute to the existing literature by analyzing the impact of pre-natal stress exposure on a child’s early cognitive and socio-emotional outcomes, which are crucial determinants of future success in school and the labor market. Our unique data allows us to exploit randomly-induced stress brought about by a large earthquake in Chile, as well as the random timing of pregnancies during and shortly after the earthquake.

²³ See Almond and Currie (2011) for a review.

Furthermore, we are able to improve on previous measures of stress that rely on exposure to an event, which were not able to identify heterogeneous individual responses to the same phenomena. Our data includes mothers' actual (self-reported) stress due to the earthquake, rather than exposure to stress.

Using a survey that contains results from several childhood development tests, as well as an extensive set of variables that describe the mother's pregnancy, her mental health background, mothers' cognitive and socio-emotional skills, and household socio-demographic information, we estimate a reduced-form model that estimates a difference-in-difference estimator of the effect of in-utero stress on several child development outcomes.

We find that in-utero stress is detrimental to childhood development. Our baseline estimates reveal that it reduces the Battelle Developmental Inventory test scores by 0.2 standard deviations. We also find that it reduces the cognitive dimension of the Childhood Learning and Development Test (TADI) by a similar magnitude, and that it increases attention problems measured by the Child Behavior Checklist. Our data allows us to rule out that the measured effect is due to alternative explanations, such as indirect physical health effects of the earthquake, changes in mothers' behaviors in response to stress, or to post-birth decisions of child care and mothers' employment. We find that these alternative explanations do not change our measured effect.

We also find suggestive evidence that the harmful effects on the two developmental tests (BDI and TADI) occur during the first trimester of pregnancy, while the effects on behavioral problems are less clear in relation to the timing of the shock during the pregnancy. Additionally, our results suggest that the harmful effects of the shocks are suffered by children in relatively low-income households, with the exception of attention problems, which are found among higher-income children. For the most part, the effects of

stress affect boys and girls similarly; however, stress reduces boys' outcomes in the BDI test and increases their attention problems. Meanwhile, girls' outcomes in the cognitive dimension of the TADI test are negatively affected.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first paper to estimate the causal impact of in-utero stress on early childhood development. We contribute to our understanding of the impact of stress suffered during pregnancy on the early years of a child's life. Our findings have relevant policy implications, because they suggest that children who suffer stress in the pre-natal period are a vulnerable group that should be monitored post-birth to provide remedial interventions, if necessary.

Our results suggest that cognitive and socio-emotional skills by age 2 are already affected by in-utero events. Furthermore, we show that these effects might start early during pregnancy (first trimester), which suggest that public policies should be focalized on early stages of pregnancy, and continue throughout the pregnancy. An additional policy implication is that birthweight as a proxy for fetal health has limitations—it is able to reveal some relevant health problems but misses others (as highlighted in Almond and Currie, 2017), so that better measures are needed. A third contribution is to highlight the relevance of generating public policies to remediate cognitive and socio-emotional effects of in utero shocks as early as possible during a child's life, and not wait until children enter school.

Our results also suggest that public policies could provide support to adults diagnosed with mental health problems if they become parents, as some of our results suggest the existence of strong negative effects of mother's mental health on child development. Finally, our study reveals the relevance of longitudinal datasets of early childhood development (such as ELPI) in the design of public policies. Furthermore, given the

heterogeneous effects found in this study, it is important that these new datasets consider the multiple dimensions of child development, which include not only cognitive skills but also socioemotional, mental health, and attention problems, among others.

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Table 1. Summary Statistics by Earthquake Regions, Maternal Stress and In-Utero exposure (2012)

Variables:	Regions:									
	All			Non-Earthquake			Earthquake			
	Obs	Mean	S.D.	Obs	Mean	S.D.	Obs	Mean	S.D.	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	
Child Development Outcomes:										
BDI test (T-scores)	1975	0.00	1.00	419	-0.07	1.01	1556	0.02	1.00	
TADI - Total (T-scores)	1960	0.01	0.99	416	0.05	1.02	1544	0.00	0.98	
TADI - Cognition (T-scores)	1960	0.01	0.99	416	0.00	1.01	1544	0.01	0.99	
TADI - Motor skills (T-scores)	1969	0.01	0.99	417	0.05	1.02	1552	0.00	0.98	
TADI - Language (T-scores)	1969	0.01	1.00	417	-0.05	1.00	1552	0.03	1.00	
TADI - Socioemotional (T-scores)	1969	0.01	0.99	417	0.16	1.02	1552	-0.03	0.98	*
CBCL - Total (T-scores)	1124	0.00	1.00	231	-0.05	1.00	893	0.01	1.00	
CBCL - Internalization (T-scores)	1124	0.00	0.99	231	-0.07	1.00	893	0.02	0.99	
CBCL - Externalization (T-scores)	1124	0.00	1.00	231	-0.03	0.98	893	0.01	1.01	
CBCL - Reactivity (percentile)	1124	64.4	17.0	231	64.4	16.9	893	64.4	17.0	
CBCL - Anxiety/Depression (percentile)	1124	68.0	17.4	231	66.4	17.1	893	68.4	17.5	
CBCL - Somatic complaint (percentile)	1124	68.8	16.9	231	66.6	16.0	893	69.3	17.1	*
CBCL - Withdrawn (percentile)	1124	72.9	15.4	231	71.8	15.4	893	73.2	15.4	
CBCL - Attention problems (percentile)	1124	72.5	15.4	231	72.4	15.7	893	72.6	15.3	
CBCL - Aggressive behavior (percentile)	1124	72.2	17.1	231	71.6	16.8	893	72.4	17.2	
CBCL - Sleep problems (percentile)	1124	65.6	14.3	231	65.9	14.4	893	65.5	14.3	
Maternal Controls										
Maternal Stress (fraction)	1975	0.36	0.48	419	0.16	0.36	1556	0.42	0.49	*
In-utero at earthquake (fraction)	1975	0.44	0.50	419	0.44	0.50	1556	0.44	0.50	
Age (years)	1975	28.3	6.9	419	27.7	6.6	1556	28.5	6.9	*
Education (years)	1975	11.7	2.7	419	11.8	2.9	1556	11.6	2.7	
Low Numeracy Skills in WAIS (fraction)	1975	0.69	0.46	419	0.67	0.47	1556	0.70	0.46	
Low Vocabulary Skills in WAIS (fraction)	1975	0.50	0.50	419	0.53	0.50	1556	0.49	0.50	
Low Extraversion in BFI (fraction)	1975	0.19	0.39	419	0.16	0.36	1556	0.20	0.40	
Low Agreeableness in BFI (fraction)	1975	0.08	0.27	419	0.08	0.27	1556	0.08	0.27	

Low Responsibility in BFI (fraction)	1975	0.06	0.23	419	0.06	0.24	1556	0.06	0.23
Low Neuroticism in BFI (fraction)	1975	0.50	0.50	419	0.51	0.50	1556	0.49	0.50
Low Openness Experience in BFI (fraction)	1975	0.08	0.28	419	0.07	0.26	1556	0.09	0.28
Child Controls									
Girl	1975	0.49	0.5	419	0.49	0.5	1556	0.49	0.5
Child's birth order	1975	1.0	0.2	419	1.0	0.2	1556	1.0	0.2
Age (months)	1975	19.3	6.6	419	19.0	6.6	1556	19.4	6.6
Number of siblings	1975	0.9	1.0	419	0.9	1.0	1556	0.9	1.0
Household/Family Controls									
Total household income per capita (\$'000)	1975	125.8	149.6	419	130.1	137.0	1556	124.6	152.8
Father lives in household (fraction)	1975	0.68	0.47	419	0.70	0.46	1556	0.67	0.47
Prior mental health issues: mother (fraction)	1975	0.13	0.34	419	0.13	0.34	1556	0.13	0.33
Prior mental health issues: father (fraction)	1975	0.02	0.14	419	0.02	0.13	1556	0.02	0.14
Prior mental health issues: relatives (fraction)	1975	0.16	0.37	419	0.15	0.36	1556	0.17	0.37
Channels									
Smoked during pregnancy (fraction)	1971	0.08	0.27	417	0.09	0.29	1554	0.07	0.26
Alcohol during pregnancy (fraction)	1974	0.08	0.27	419	0.08	0.27	1555	0.08	0.26
Recreational drugs during pregnancy (fraction)	1971	0.02	0.12	418	0.01	0.10	1553	0.02	0.13
Labor complications (number)	1975	0.25	0.50	419	0.26	0.52	1556	0.24	0.49
Premature birth (<37 weeks) (fraction)	1975	0.11	0.31	419	0.10	0.30	1556	0.11	0.31
Weight-for-height (z-score)	1881	0.01	1.00	397	0.01	0.98	1484	0.01	1.00
Formal (external) childcare (fraction)	1975	0.05	0.17	419	0.04	0.15	1556	0.05	0.17
Months employed after earthquake	1975	3.0	3.4	419	3.0	3.4	1556	3.0	3.4

Source: Author's calculations using ELPI 2012 data. Chile is divided into 15 administrative regions. Earthquake regions: V, VI, VII, VIII, IX and XIII (Metropolitan region). Non-earthquake regions: I, II, III, IV, X, XI, XII, XIV, XV. *: Difference between areas affected and not affected by earthquake is statistically significant at the 5% level.

Table 2. Mothers reporting stress symptoms after the earthquake, ELPI 2012 (percentage)

Stress Symptoms:	Non-Earthquake Region	Earthquake Region
Insomnia	1.7	12.1
Stress, anguish or anxiety	3.0	12.3
Crying or emotional instability	2.2	10.7
Fear or panic	11.4	30.2
Traumatic memories	0.6	7.9
Others	0.6	1.3
Any symptom ^a	15.1	40.8
Number of obs.	537	1,892

Source: Author's calculations using ELPI 2012 data. Mother's asked whether they suffered a series of symptoms that she could attribute to the earthquake. All differences are statistically significant at the 1% level.

Chile is divided into 15 administrative regions. Earthquake regions: V, VI, VII, VIII, IX and XIII (Metropolitan region). Non-earthquake regions: I, II, III, IV, X, XI, XII, XIV, XV.

^a: Excludes the "Others" category.

VARIABLES	Earthquake region			Earthquake intensity		
	Batelle	TADI	CBCL	Batelle	TADI	CBCL
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Earthquake-affected x In utero at quake	-0.1028 (0.130)	-0.0966 (0.122)	-0.0366 (0.108)	-0.0104 (0.019)	-0.0085 (0.017)	0.0004 (0.016)
Earthquake-affected residence	-0.3303*** (0.099)	-0.5068*** (0.164)	-0.4619 (0.298)	-0.0559 (0.060)	-0.1436** (0.069)	-0.0432 (0.126)
In-utero at earthquake	-0.0707 (0.145)	0.2329* (0.128)	-0.0192 (0.104)	-0.0960 (0.143)	0.2025 (0.127)	-0.0507 (0.108)
Prior mental health issues (mother)	0.0558 (0.064)	-0.0102 (0.062)	0.1818** (0.090)	0.0580 (0.065)	-0.0037 (0.062)	0.1815** (0.089)
Prior mental health issues (father)	0.0819 (0.162)	-0.0341 (0.174)	0.1933 (0.141)	0.0820 (0.160)	-0.0336 (0.175)	0.1941 (0.141)
Prior mental health issues (relative)	0.0474 (0.064)	0.1109** (0.051)	0.0637 (0.070)	0.0511 (0.063)	0.1214** (0.052)	0.0677 (0.071)
Girl	0.1631*** (0.049)	0.0979** (0.044)	-0.0202 (0.054)	0.1621*** (0.049)	0.0969** (0.044)	-0.0206 (0.055)
Child's birth order	-0.1327 (0.114)	-0.1729 (0.140)	0.1483 (0.135)	-0.1283 (0.114)	-0.1625 (0.140)	0.1516 (0.134)
Age (months)	0.0164** (0.007)	-0.0143** (0.006)	0.0015 (0.011)	0.0165** (0.007)	-0.0142** (0.006)	0.0015 (0.011)
Total hhold income per capita (\$)	0.0000 (0.000)	0.0000 (0.000)	-0.0000*** (0.000)	0.0000 (0.000)	0.0000* (0.000)	-0.0000*** (0.000)
Number of siblings	-0.0285 (0.030)	-0.0271 (0.031)	-0.0204 (0.032)	-0.0296 (0.030)	-0.0289 (0.031)	-0.0215 (0.032)
Father lives in hhold	0.0681 (0.054)	0.0396 (0.053)	-0.0169 (0.075)	0.0660 (0.054)	0.0353 (0.053)	-0.0190 (0.074)

Mother's educ (years)	0.0196*	0.0207**	-0.0126	0.0202*	0.0222**	-0.0123
	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.012)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.013)
Mother-Low Numeracy Skills	0.0284	-0.1473***	0.0386	0.0283	-0.1479***	0.0395
	(0.056)	(0.052)	(0.069)	(0.056)	(0.052)	(0.069)
Mother-Low Vocabulary Skills	0.0308	0.0349	0.0511	0.0312	0.0362	0.0512
	(0.048)	(0.051)	(0.069)	(0.048)	(0.051)	(0.069)
Mother-Low Extraversion (BFI)	-0.1536**	-0.0895	0.2067***	-0.1555**	-0.0934	0.2056***
	(0.066)	(0.059)	(0.074)	(0.066)	(0.059)	(0.074)
Mother-Low Agreeableness (BFI)	-0.0890	-0.2367***	0.1996*	-0.0901	-0.2392***	0.2002*
	(0.082)	(0.071)	(0.106)	(0.082)	(0.071)	(0.106)
Mother-Low Responsibility (BFI)	-0.3171**	-0.0900	-0.3100*	-0.3146**	-0.0867	-0.3110*
	(0.135)	(0.120)	(0.172)	(0.136)	(0.121)	(0.171)
Mother-High Neuroticism (BFI)	-0.1196***	-0.0323	0.3395***	-0.1186**	-0.0315	0.3402***
	(0.045)	(0.051)	(0.054)	(0.046)	(0.051)	(0.054)
Mother-Low Openness Exper. (BFI)	-0.1786**	-0.0933	0.0490	-0.1753*	-0.0845	0.0511
	(0.089)	(0.085)	(0.099)	(0.089)	(0.085)	(0.097)
Observations	1,945	2,031	1,196	1,945	2,031	1,196
R-squared	0.076	0.070	0.100	0.076	0.073	0.100

Constant not shown. Dependent variable is the standardized T-score obtained in each test; BDI = Batelle Development Inventory; TADI = Childhood Learning and Development Test; CBCL = Child Behavior Checklist. In columns (1) through (3): Earthquake-affected = 1 if mother lived in municipality affected by earthquake; in columns (4) through (6), earthquake-affected = intensity of earthquake in mother's municipality, as measured by Mercalli scale (non-affected regions = 0). Additional controls: region dummy variables. Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10.

Table 4. Effect of Maternal Stress on Early Childhood Development Tests

Variables:	All Children			Earthquake Regions		
	BDI (1)	TADI (2)	CBCL (3)	BDI (4)	TADI (5)	CBCL (6)
Maternal Stress x In utero at quake	-0.167* (0.0888)	-0.0910 (0.0844)	0.0937 (0.126)	-0.186* (0.0987)	-0.0855 (0.0918)	0.0502 (0.131)
Observations	1,975	2,062	1,217	1,556	1,615	958
R-squared	0.078	0.065	0.104	0.062	0.047	0.089

Constant not shown. Dependent variable is the standardized T-score obtained in each test; BDI = Batelle Development Inventory; TADI = Childhood Learning and Development Test; CBCL = Child Behavior Checklist. Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10. Additional controls (not shown): Child's: sex, birth order, and age (months); mother's: age, education, numeracy and vocabulary skills (WAIS test), and problem scores on Big Five Inventory characteristics (extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism, and openness to new experiences); prior mental health issues reported by: mother, father, or other close relative; total household income per capita (Chilean pesos), number of siblings; indicator for whether the child's father lives in the household; and region dummy variables

Table 5. Earthquake Intensity and Maternal Stress

VARIABLES	<i>Dependent variable:</i>		
	<i>Suffered Earthquake-induced Maternal stress</i>		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
Earthquake intensity	0.0370*** (0.00648)	0.0369*** (0.00634)	0.0366*** (0.00632)
Prior mental health issues (mother)		0.123*** (0.0324)	0.0974*** (0.0327)
Prior mental health issues (father)		0.0104 (0.0787)	0.0214 (0.0728)
Prior mental health issues (relative)		0.0215 (0.0299)	0.0276 (0.0299)
Total household income per capita (\$)			-2.49e-07*** (7.48e-08)
Number of siblings			0.000529 (0.0132)
Father lives in household			0.0402 (0.0262)
Mother's age (years)			0.000830 (0.00160)
Mother's educ. (years)			-0.00784* (0.00428)
Mother-Low Numeracy Skills (WAIS)			0.00324 (0.0238)
Mother-Low Vocabulary Skills (WAIS)			0.0550** (0.0229)
Mother-Low Extraversion (BFI)			-0.0368 (0.0253)
Mother-Low Agreeableness (BFI)			-0.00213 (0.0351)
Mother-Low Responsibility (BFI)			-0.0176 (0.0440)
Mother-Low Neuroticism (BFI)			-0.0886*** (0.0192)
Mother-Low Openness Experience (BFI)			-0.0311 (0.0460)
Observations	2,124	2,124	2,124
R-squared	0.048	0.056	0.083

Source: Author's calculations using ELPI 2012 data. Earthquake intensity is measured at the municipal level with a Modified Mercalli scale (see Appendix 1) theoretically ranging from 1 to 12. In our data the maximum value is 9. Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics Before and After 2010 Earthquake (CASEN-EPT)

Variables:	Region:			
	Non-Earthquake		Earthquake	
	2009	2010	2009	2010
Mental health/stress symptoms (Frequency)	n.a.	2.3	n.a.	6.0
Mental health/stress symptoms (Intensity)	n.a.	2.2	n.a.	5.6
Fetal Mortality (Rate/1,000 born)	8.6	8.8	9.2	9.4
Rural area (Fraction)	0.31	0.31	0.29	0.29
Married (Fraction)	0.32	0.32	0.37	0.37
Education (Years)	10.1	10.2	10.3	10.3
Working (Fraction)	0.72	0.72	0.69	0.67
Working at least 1 hour last week (Fraction)	0.69	0.7	0.67	0.66
General Health, self-reported index (1-7)	5.6	5.7	5.6	5.6
Housing Global Quality (1-3)	1.31	1.26	1.30	1.30
Outward Appearance Index (1-3)	1.33	1.46	1.30	1.55
Household Income (CL \$'000)	653	590	551	503

Source: Author's calculations using CASEN 2009 and CASEN-EPT 2010 data. Chile is divided into 15 administrative regions. Earthquake regions: V, VI, VII, VIII, IX and XIII (Metropolitan region). Non-earthquake regions: I, II, III, IV, X, XI, XII, XIV, XV. Mental Health is measured on a 0-68 point scale, based on the frequency and intensity of the following symptoms of the 27-F earthquake/tsunami: painful memories, nightmares, reliving event, memory-induced physical symptoms, avoidance of feelings or memories of the event, avoidance of activities that elicit memories of the event, cannot remember important parts of the event; and more general symptoms such as inability to enjoy every day activities, feel distant from other people, incapable of feeling sadness or affection, difficulty projecting a long and productive life, trouble sleeping, irritability, inability to concentrate, easily distracted, and/or easily frightened. All the statistics reported are for females aged between 15-59 years old. General Health varies from 1 equal to very bad, to 7 equal to very good. Housing Global Quality and Outward Appearance Index are measured by the following scale: Acceptable=1, Recoverable=2 and Not Recoverable=3.

Table 7. Maternal Stress and Early Childhood Development: Alternative channels

Variables:	Channels:								
	None (Baseline) (1)	Labor Complic. (2)	Pre- mature birth (3)	Weight at birth (4)	Smoked (5)	Alcohol (6)	Drugs (7)	Child- care (8)	Worked after 27F (9)
A. Dependent Variable: BDI									
Stress x In utero at quake	-0.167* (0.0888)	-0.162* (0.0892)	-0.164* (0.0889)	-0.174* (0.0913)	-0.171* (0.0895)	-0.166* (0.0891)	-0.170* (0.0888)	-0.162* (0.0884)	-0.168* (0.0886)
Channel		-0.115*** (0.0428)	-0.160** (0.0724)	0.0323 (0.0211)	-0.0586 (0.0957)	-0.117 (0.0843)	-0.238 (0.204)	0.164 (0.115)	0.00564 (0.00742)
Observations	1,975	1,975	1,975	1,881	1,971	1,974	1,971	1,975	1,975
R-squared	0.078	0.081	0.080	0.073	0.078	0.079	0.079	0.079	0.078
B. Dependent Variable: TADI									
Stress x In utero at quake	-0.0910 (0.0844)	-0.0888 (0.0855)	-0.0875 (0.0841)	-0.0891 (0.0878)	-0.0947 (0.0850)	-0.0889 (0.0832)	-0.0901 (0.0839)	-0.0812 (0.0848)	-0.0925 (0.0838)
Channel		-0.0840* (0.0473)	-0.228*** (0.0735)	0.0507** (0.0226)	-0.0539 (0.0808)	-0.197** (0.0774)	-0.0863 (0.198)	0.321** (0.125)	0.00659 (0.00667)
Observations	2,062	2,062	2,062	1,963	2,058	2,060	2,057	2,062	2,062
R-squared	0.065	0.067	0.070	0.064	0.064	0.068	0.065	0.068	0.066
C. Dependent Variable: Child Behavior Checklist - Total Score									
Stress x In utero at quake	0.0937 (0.126)	0.0913 (0.126)	0.0970 (0.126)	0.0701 (0.130)	0.0939 (0.125)	0.0939 (0.125)	0.0964 (0.126)	0.0979 (0.127)	0.0962 (0.125)
Channel		0.103 (0.0695)	0.0775 (0.0873)	-0.0430 (0.0292)	0.0958 (0.111)	0.121 (0.0896)	-0.255 (0.185)	0.0965 (0.154)	-0.00866 (0.00887)
Observations	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,154	1,217	1,216	1,214	1,217	1,217
R-squared	0.104	0.107	0.105	0.106	0.105	0.105	0.105	0.105	0.105

Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$. Constant not shown. Dependent variable is the standardized T-score obtained in each test. Channels are: number of complications during labor; whether the child was premature (<37 weeks), child's weight-for-height at birth (z-score); whether the mother smoked, drank alcohol, or consumed recreational drugs during pregnancy; whether the child attended formal child care (% months since birth); and the number of months the mother worked in the 6 months after the earthquake. Additional controls (not shown): Child's: sex, birth order, and age (months); mother's: age, education, numeracy and vocabulary skills (WAIS test), and problem scores on Big Five Inventory characteristics (extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism, and openness to new experiences); prior mental health issues reported by: mother, father, or other close relative; total household income per capita (Chilean pesos), number of siblings; indicator for whether the child's father lives in the household; and region dummy variables.

Table 8. Maternal Stress and Early Childhood Development: Alternative channels

Variable:	Dependent Variable:							
	Labor Complic. (1)	Pre-mature (2)	Weight at birth (3)	Smoked (4)	Alcohol (5)	Drugs (6)	Child-care (7)	Worked after 27F (8)
Stress x In utero at quake	0.0257 (0.0470)	0.00706 (0.0259)	0.00911 (0.0919)	-0.0180 (0.0244)	-0.0105 (0.0272)	0.00820 (0.00985)	-0.0296* (0.0155)	0.217 (0.271)
Observations	2,081	2,081	1,982	2,077	2,079	2,076	2,081	2,081
R-squared	0.026	0.034	0.042	0.056	0.031	0.022	0.045	0.218

Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10. Constant not shown. Channels are: number of complications during labor; whether the child was premature (<37 weeks), child's weight-for-height at birth (z-score); whether the mother smoked, drank alcohol, or consumed recreational drugs during pregnancy; whether the child attended formal child care (% months since birth); and the number of months the mother worked in the 6 months after the earthquake. Additional controls (not shown): Child's: sex, birth order, and age (months); mother's: age, education, numeracy and vocabulary skills (WAIS test), and problem scores on Big Five Inventory characteristics (extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism, and openness to new experiences); prior mental health issues reported by: mother, father, or other close relative; total household income per capita (Chilean pesos), number of siblings; indicator for whether the child's father lives in the household; and region dummy variables.

Table 9. Effect of Maternal Stress on Early Childhood Development Tests: TADI

Variable:	TADI Tests				
	Total (1)	Cognition (2)	Motor skills (3)	Language (4)	Socio- emotional (5)
Stress x In utero at quake	-0.0910 (0.0844)	-0.168* (0.0891)	-0.0720 (0.0887)	-0.0186 (0.0870)	-0.0112 (0.0808)
Observations	2,062	2,062	2,072	2,072	2,072
R-squared	0.065	0.054	0.044	0.055	0.070

TADI = Childhood Learning and Development Test.

Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$. Constant not shown. Dependent variable is the standardized T-score obtained in each test. Additional controls: Child's: sex, birth order, and age (months); mother's: age, education, numeracy and vocabulary skills (WAIS test), and low score on Big Five Inventory characteristics (extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism, and openness to new experiences); prior mental health issues reported by: mother, father, or other close relative; total household income per capita (pesos), number of siblings; indicator for whether the child's father lives in the household; and region dummy variables.

Table 10. Effect of Maternal Stress on Child Behavior Checklist (specific areas)

Variable:	Total	Interna- lization	Externa- lization	Reac- tivity	Anxiety/ Depression	Somatic complaints	With- drawn	Attention problems	Aggressive behavior	Sleep problems
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
Stress x In utero at quake	0.0937 (0.126)	0.0473 (0.137)	0.0905 (0.126)	1.325 (2.443)	2.086 (2.523)	-1.530 (2.383)	1.765 (1.835)	3.885* (2.076)	-0.289 (2.250)	2.596 (1.882)
Observations	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,217
R-squared	0.104	0.091	0.090	0.072	0.118	0.075	0.048	0.067	0.096	0.092

Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$. Constant not shown. Dependent variable: Child behavior problem (standard deviation of percentile in distribution of problem area). Additional controls: Child's: sex, birth order, and age (months); mother's: age, education, numeracy and vocabulary skills (WAIS test), and problem scores on Big Five Inventory characteristics (extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism, and openness to new experiences); prior mental health issues reported by: mother, father, or other close relative; total household income per capita (pesos), number of siblings; indicator for whether the child's father lives in the household; and region dummy variables.

Table 11. Effect of Maternal Stress on Early Childhood Development - by Trimester of Pregnancy at time of shock (continues)

In-utero Maternal stress during:	BDI Test (1)	TADI Tests				
		Total (2)	Cognition (3)	Motor skills (4)	Language (5)	Socio-emotional (6)
1st Trimester	-0.227* (0.117)	-0.106 (0.115)	0.0569 (0.128)	-0.0273 (0.126)	-0.138 (0.121)	-0.199* (0.110)
2nd Trimester	-0.0590 (0.0983)	-0.0292 (0.137)	-0.138 (0.136)	-0.00363 (0.117)	-0.00371 (0.140)	0.0617 (0.116)
3rd Trimester	-0.0158 (0.0810)	-0.0199 (0.104)	-0.0868 (0.0999)	0.0402 (0.106)	0.0814 (0.103)	-0.117 (0.0973)
Observations	865	917	917	919	919	919
R-squared	0.226	0.105	0.087	0.075	0.117	0.100

BDI = Batelle Development Inventory; TADI = Childhood Learning and Development Test; CBCL = Child Behavior Checklist. BDI, TADI and CBCL Total tests measured as standardized T-scores. Specific CBCL problems measured as percentile of problem distribution. Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10. Includes children whose mothers were pregnant at time of earthquake. Constant not shown. Additional controls: Child's: sex, birth order, and age (months); mother's: age, education, numeracy and vocabulary skills (WAIS test), and problem scores on Big Five Inventory characteristics (extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism, and openness to new experiences); prior mental health issues reported by: mother, father, or other close relative; total household income per capita (pesos), number of siblings; indicator for whether the child's father lives in the household; and region dummy variables.

Table 11 (continued). Effect of Maternal Stress on Early Childhood Development - by Trimester of Pregnancy at time of shock

In-utero Maternal stress during:	Child Behavior Check List Test							
	Total (7)	Reac- tivity (8)	Anxiety/ Depression (9)	Somatic complaints (10)	With- drawn (11)	Attention problems (12)	Aggressive behavior (13)	Sleep problems (14)
1st Trimester	0.143 (0.102)	0.621 (2.054)	1.901 (1.943)	1.871 (2.083)	-0.259 (1.838)	4.351** (1.786)	2.650 (2.016)	2.506 (1.718)
2nd Trimester	0.117 (0.144)	1.252 (1.850)	1.695 (2.192)	0.314 (2.157)	1.991 (1.751)	-1.166 (2.091)	0.904 (2.445)	4.738** (1.925)
3rd Trimester	0.222* (0.114)	2.408 (1.910)	3.663* (2.160)	-0.738 (1.999)	0.0354 (1.854)	3.481** (1.632)	2.655 (1.769)	2.205 (1.565)
Observations	917	917	917	917	917	917	917	917
R-squared	0.108	0.075	0.124	0.078	0.058	0.081	0.110	0.093

BDI, TADI and CBCL Total tests measured as standardized T-scores. Specific CBCL problems measured as percentile of problem distribution. Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10. Includes children whose mothers were pregnant at time of earthquake. Constant not shown. Additional controls: Child's: sex, birth order, and age (months); mother's: age, education, numeracy and vocabulary skills (WAIS test), and problem scores on Big Five Inventory characteristics (extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism, and openness to new experiences); prior mental health issues reported by: mother, father, or other close relative; total household income per capita (pesos), number of siblings; indicator for whether the child's father lives in the household; and region dummy variables.

Table 12. Effect of Maternal Stress on Early Childhood Development - By Household's Income Level

In-utero Maternal by Household Income:	BDI Test (1)	TADI Tests				
		Total (2)	Cognition (3)	Motor skills (4)	Language (5)	Socio-emotional (6)
Stress In Utero x Low Income	-0.209* (0.122)	-0.214* (0.121)	-0.320** (0.128)	-0.0889 (0.132)	-0.0931 (0.112)	-0.114 (0.101)
Stress In Utero x High Income	-0.169 (0.120)	0.0274 (0.126)	0.0161 (0.135)	-0.166 (0.107)	0.0824 (0.124)	0.146 (0.129)
Observations	1,578	1,666	1,666	1,673	1,673	1,673
R-squared	0.083	0.079	0.067	0.054	0.065	0.075

BDI, TADI and CBCL Total tests measured as standardized T-scores. Specific CBCL problems measured as percentile of problem distribution. Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10. Includes children in all areas. Low (High)-income: household income per capita below (above) median. Constant not shown. Additional controls: Child's: sex, birth order, and age (months); mother's: age, education, numeracy and vocabulary skills (WAIS test), and problem scores on Big Five Inventory characteristics (extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism, and openness to new experiences); prior mental health issues reported by: mother, father, or other close relative; total household income per capita (pesos), number of siblings; indicator for whether the child's father lives in the household; and region dummy variables.

Table 12 (continued). Effect of Maternal Stress on Early Childhood Development - By Household's Income Level

In-utero Maternal by Household Income:	Child Behavior Check List Test							
	Total	Reac- tivity	Anxiety/ Depression	Somatic complaints	With- drawn	Attention problems	Aggressive behavior	Sleep problems
	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)
Stress In Utero x Low Income	0.101 (0.151)	2.457 (2.675)	0.428 (2.943)	-0.445 (2.810)	3.349 (2.074)	2.948 (2.478)	-1.429 (2.748)	2.626 (2.230)
Stress In Utero x High Income	0.132 (0.183)	3.254 (3.242)	1.280 (3.503)	0.766 (3.030)	-0.434 (2.657)	6.301** (2.830)	-0.00632 (3.256)	3.285 (2.654)
Observations	986	986	986	986	986	986	986	986
R-squared	0.107	0.085	0.118	0.088	0.060	0.071	0.100	0.100

BDI, TADI and CBCL Total tests measured as standardized T-scores. Specific CBCL problems measured as percentile of problem distribution. Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10. Includes children whose mothers were pregnant at time of earthquake. Constant not shown. Additional controls: Child's: sex, birth order, and age (months); mother's: age, education, numeracy and vocabulary skills (WAIS test), and problem scores on Big Five Inventory characteristics (extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism, and openness to new experiences); prior mental health issues reported by: mother, father, or other close relative; total household income per capita (pesos), number of siblings; indicator for whether the child's father lives in the household; and region dummy variables.

Table 13. Effect of Maternal Stress on Early Childhood Development - By child's sex

In-utero Maternal stress by Child's sex:	BDI Test	TADI Tests				
		Total	Cognition	Motor skills	Language	Socio-emotional
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Stress In Utero x Girl	-0.0992 (0.0883)	-0.0468 (0.0914)	-0.202** (0.100)	0.00869 (0.0984)	0.0147 (0.0899)	0.0354 (0.0923)
Stress In Utero x Boy	-0.244** (0.116)	-0.140 (0.112)	-0.129 (0.109)	-0.161 (0.115)	-0.0555 (0.117)	-0.0630 (0.107)
Observations	1,975	2,062	2,062	2,072	2,072	2,072
R-squared	0.079	0.066	0.054	0.045	0.055	0.071

BDI, TADI and CBCL Total tests measured as standardized T-scores. Specific CBCL problems measured as percentile of problem distribution. Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10. Includes children in all areas. Low (High)-income: household income per capita below (above) median. Constant not shown. Additional controls: Child's: sex, birth order, and age (months); mother's: age, education, numeracy and vocabulary skills (WAIS test), and problem scores on Big Five Inventory characteristics (extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism, and openness to new experiences); prior mental health issues reported by: mother, father, or other close relative; total household income per capita (pesos), number of siblings; indicator for whether the child's father lives in the household; and region dummy variables.

Table 13 (continued). Effect of Maternal Stress on Early Childhood Development - By child's sex

In-utero Maternal stress by Child's sex:	Child Behavior Check List Test							
	Total (7)	Reac-tivity (8)	Anxiety/Depression (9)	Somatic complaints (10)	With-drawn (11)	Attention problems (12)	Aggressive behavior (13)	Sleep problems (14)
Stress In Utero x Girl	0.0638 (0.130)	-0.0239 (2.659)	2.254 (2.759)	-0.638 (2.545)	0.852 (1.795)	3.442 (2.363)	-1.752 (2.301)	1.842 (1.978)
Stress In Utero x Boy	0.126 (0.147)	2.758 (2.769)	1.908 (2.614)	-2.479 (2.746)	2.735 (2.352)	4.355** (2.111)	1.266 (2.672)	3.399 (2.104)
Observations	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,217	1,217
R-squared	0.104	0.074	0.118	0.075	0.049	0.093	0.067	0.097

BDI, TADI and CBCL Total tests measured as standardized T-scores. Specific CBCL problems measured as percentile of problem distribution. Robust standard errors in parentheses. Errors clustered at the municipality level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.10. Includes children whose mothers were pregnant at time of earthquake. Constant not shown. Additional controls: Child's: sex, birth order, and age (months); mother's: age, education, numeracy and vocabulary skills (WAIS test), and problem scores on Big Five Inventory characteristics (extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism, and openness to new experiences); prior mental health issues reported by: mother, father, or other close relative; total household income per capita (pesos), number of siblings; indicator for whether the child's father lives in the household; and region dummy variables.

APPENDIX 1

Table A1.1. Description of the Modified Mercalli Intensity categories.

Intensity	Description of Shaking/Damage
I	Not felt except by a very few under especially favorable conditions.
II	Felt only by a few persons at rest, especially on upper floors of buildings.
III	Felt quite noticeably by persons indoors, especially on upper floors of buildings. Many people do not recognize it as an earthquake. Standing motor cars may rock slightly. Vibrations similar to the passing of a truck. Duration estimated.
IV	Felt indoors by many, outdoors by few during the day. At night, some awakened. Dishes, windows, doors disturbed; walls make cracking sound. Sensation like heavy truck striking building. Standing motor cars rocked noticeably.
V	Felt by nearly everyone; many awakened. Some dishes, windows broken. Unstable objects overturned. Pendulum clocks may stop.
VI	Felt by all, many frightened. Some heavy furniture moved; a few instances of fallen plaster. Damage slight.
VII	Damage negligible in buildings of good design and construction; slight to moderate in well-built ordinary structures; considerable damage in poorly built or badly designed structures; some chimneys broken.
VIII	Damage slight in specially designed structures; considerable damage in ordinary substantial buildings with partial collapse. Damage great in poorly built structures. Fall of chimneys, factory stacks, columns, monuments, walls. Heavy furniture overturned.
IX	Damage considerable in specially designed structures; well-designed frame structures thrown out of plumb. Damage great in substantial buildings, with partial collapse. Buildings shifted off foundations.
X	Some well-built wooden structures destroyed; most masonry and frame structures destroyed with foundations. Rails bent.
XI	Few, if any (masonry) structures remain standing. Bridges destroyed. Rails bent greatly.
XII	Damage total. Lines of sight and level are distorted. Objects thrown into the air.

Source: American Red Cross Multi-Disciplinary Team (2011). Categories are based on observation, and not measurements made by instruments.

Figure A1.1. Estimated Municipal Intensities: Earthquake of 27 February 2010, Chile.

Source: Own elaboration based on Astroza et al. (2010).